

ISic4381

Fragmentary Greek epitaph

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Excavated (between 1991 and 1997) in the southern necropolis, in re-use in the wall of a now-demolished late C18 house, isolato 83, IV comparto, via C. Battisti

Coordinates

38.183179, 15.549449

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 10771

Physical Description

Three joining fragments of a white marble plaque, of which the upper left corner and lower right corner are missing; minor damage to the upper right corner also.

Dimensions

Height 20.5 cm

Width 24.5 cm

Depth 1.5 cm

Layout

Remains of four lines of Greek letters, approximately centred on the stone. The beginning of lines 1 and 2 is lost, and the end of line 4 is damaged.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular quadrate letters, with a rhomboid omicron and regular sigma; epsilon has bars of equal length. Vertical strokes appear to serve as interpuncts in line 1 and to demarcate the number in line 4.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 21 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Θ(εοῖς)] · Κα(ταχθονίοις)
2. [---]γνητος
3. ἔζησεν
4. ἔτη · μ ·

Apparatus

Text after Zavettieri 2017 and photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. [--]gnetos lived 40 years

Translation (it)

Agli dei inferi. [--]gneto visse anni 40

Commentary

The beginning of the name in line 2 is lost. The available names in [--]νητος are relatively few (LGPN lists some 17 different names ending in -νητος, of which several are either very rare or too long. The three most common, and the only ones attested in Sicily are Ἀφθόνητος, Διόγνητος, and Θεόγνητος, of which the latter two are more likely, since the trace visible on the photo before the ν is most readily compatible with a γ.

Digital identifiers:**Bibliography**

Zavettieri, G. 2017. Le epigrafi. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 167-171. At 169 no.4 fig.4
Bacci, G. M., Tigano, G.2001. *Da Zancle a Messina, un percorso archeologico attraverso gli scavi*. Messina. At 89 CBI/5 fig.18

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archivio fotografico della soprintendenza di Messina

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